

PRODUCTION OF AMMONIUM NITRATE

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Annotation: In this article, information was given about the production of ammonium nitrate and what should be done for it. They also talked about what ammonia is and how to get saltpeter from it.

Key words: NH_3 (g) + HNO_3 (l) NH_4NO_3 +144.9 KJ Ammonium nitrate, Ammonium, acid heater; ammonia heater; ITN devices; neutralizer; evaporator; pressure tank; granulators; fans; washing machine; drum

INTRODUCTION

Is obtained by neutralizing nitric acid according to the reaction with gaseous ammonia:

This almost irreversible reaction proceeds at a high rate and with the release of a significant amount of heat. It is usually carried out under close to atmospheric pressure; in some countries, neutralization plants operate at a pressure of 0.34 MPa. In the production of ammonium nitrate, diluted 47-60% nitric acid is used. The heat of the neutralization reaction is used to evaporate the water and concentrate the solution.

MAIN BODY

Industrial production includes the following stages: neutralization of nitric acid with gaseous ammonia in the ITN apparatus (using the heat of neutralization); saltpeter solution evaporation, saltpeter solution granulation, granule cooling, surfactant granule processing, saltpeter packaging, storage and loading, waste gas and wastewater treatment. Additives are introduced during the neutralization process of nitric acid.

1 - acid heater; 2 - ammonia heater; 3 - ITN devices; 4 - neutralizer; 5 - evaporator; 6 - pressure tank; 7, 8 - granulators; 9, 23 - fans; 10 - washing machine; 11 - drum; 12.14 - conveyors; 13 - elevator; 15-fluidized bed apparatus; 16 - granulation tower;

17 - assembly; 18, 20 - pumps; 19 - swimming tank; 21-filter for swimming; 22 - air heater

The incoming 58-60% nitric acid is heated in a heater from 1 to 70-80 °C with juice steam from the ITN 3 apparatus and given for neutralization. Before apparatus 3, thermal phosphorus and sulfuric acids are added to nitric acid in the amount of 0.3-0.5% P₂O₅ and 0.05-0.2% ammonium sulfate, which is the finished product. Sulfuric and phosphoric acids are supplied by piston pumps, which are easy to operate and precisely regulated. The device is equipped with two neutralizing devices that work in parallel. Gaseous ammonia is also supplied here, heated in 2 heaters with steam condensate, up to 120-130 °C. The amount of nitric acid and ammonia supplied is regulated so that there is a slight excess of nitric acid in the solution at the outlet of the ITN apparatus, ensuring complete absorption of ammonia. At the bottom of the device, acids are neutralized at a temperature of 155-170 °C to obtain a solution containing 91-92% NH₄NO₃. At the top of the device, water vapor (called juice vapor) is washed from the splash of ammonium nitrate and HNO₃ vapor. Part of the heat from the juice vapor is used to heat the nitric acid. Next, the juice is sent for cleaning in steam scrubbers and then released to the atmosphere. An acidic solution of ammonium nitrate is sent to the neutralizer 4, where ammonia is supplied in the amount necessary to neutralize the solution. Then the solution is fed to the evaporator 5 in the upper part, which is passed with water vapor at a pressure of 1.4 MPa and air heated to about 180 °C. The resulting solution consists of 99.8-99.7% saltpeter, passes through a filter 21 at 175 °C and is sent to a pressure vessel 5 through a centrifugal submersible pump 20, and then to a rectangular metal 11 in length 16 is given to the granulation tower. m, the width is 8 m and the height of the cone from the top is 52.8 m. Granulators 7 and 8 at the top of the tower; air is supplied to the lower part of the tower, the cooling drops of saltpeter turn into granules. The drop height of saltpeter particles is 50--55 m. The design of the granulators ensures the production of granules with the same granulometric composition with a minimum amount of small granules, which reduces the penetration of dust from the tower by air. The temperature of the granules at the outlet of the tower is 90--110 °C, so they are sent to the fluidized bed apparatus for

cooling 15. The fluidized bed apparatus is a rectangular apparatus with three parts and equipped with a grid with holes. . Air is supplied by fans from under the grate, thereby creating a fluidized layer of saltpeter granules 100--150 mm high, which come from the granulation tower through a conveyor. There is an intensive cooling of granules up to a temperature of 40 ° C (but not higher than 50 ° C), which corresponds to the conditions of the existence of the IV modification. If the temperature of the cooling air is below 15 ° C, then the air is heated to 20 ° C in the heat exchanger before entering the fluidized bed apparatus. In the cold period, 1-2 sections can be used.

Air from apparatus 15 enters the granulation tower for granulation and cooling.

From the fluidized bed apparatus, the ammonium nitrate granules are transported by conveyor 14 to the rotating drum 11 for surfactant treatment. Here, the granules are sprayed with a 40% aqueous solution of NF dispersant. After that, the saltpeter passes through an electromagnetic separator to separate the accidentally caught metal objects and is sent to the hopper, then weighed and packed in paper or polythene bags. The bags are loaded onto wagons or into a warehouse via a conveyor.

The air exiting the top of the granulation tower is contaminated with ammonium nitrate particles, the juice vapor from the neutralizer and the steam-air mixture from the evaporator contain unreacted ammonia and nitric acid and entrained ammonium nitrate particles. To clean the upper part of the granulation tower, six parallel washing plate-type cleaning devices 10 are installed, which are watered with a 20-30% ammonium nitrate solution, which is supplied by a pump 18 from the tank. A portion of this solution is directed to the ITN neutralizer to wash the juice vapor and then mixed with the ammoniacal nitrate solution and thus goes to product production.¹

Part of the solution (20-30%) is constantly removed from the cycle, so the cycle ends and is replenished by adding water. At the outlet of each scrubber, a fan 9 with a capacity of 100,000 m³ / h is installed, which sucks air from the granulation tower and releases it into the atmosphere.

Ammonium nitrate or ammonium nitrate, NH₄NO₃ is a white crystalline substance containing 35% nitrogen in ammonium and nitrate forms, both forms of nitrogen are readily absorbed by plants. Granular ammonium nitrate is widely used

before planting and for all types of top dressing. On a smaller scale, it is used to manufacture explosives.

Ammonium nitrate dissolves well in water and has a high hygroscopicity (ability to absorb moisture from the air), which causes the fertilizer granules to disperse, lose their crystal form, and the fertilizers harden - the bulk material turns into a solid monolithic mass .

Schematic diagram of the production of ammonium nitrate:

A number of technological methods are used to obtain practical non-stick ammonium nitrate. An effective means of reducing the rate of moisture absorption by hygroscopic salts is their granulation. The total surface area of homogeneous granules is less than the surface area of the same amount of fine crystalline salt, so granular fertilizers absorb moisture more slowly.

Ammonium phosphates, potassium chloride, magnesium nitrate are also used as additives with the same effect. The production process of ammonium nitrate is based on the heterogeneous reaction of the interaction of gaseous ammonia with a solution of nitric acid:

The chemical reaction proceeds at high speed; in an industrial reactor it is limited by the dissolution of the gas in the liquid. Mixing the reactants is of great importance to reduce the diffusion delay.

In addition to the stage of neutralization of nitric acid with ammonia, the technological process of production of ammonium nitrate includes the stages of evaporation of the nitrate solution, granulation of the solution, cooling of the granules, treatment of the granules with surfactants, packaging, storage and loading. saltpeter, gas waste and wastewater treatment. In the form. Figure 8.8 shows a diagram of a modern large-capacity unit for the production of ammonium nitrate AS-72 with a capacity of 1360 tons per day. The original 58-60% nitric acid is heated to 70-80°C in a heater with juice vapors from the ITN 3 apparatus and given for neutralization. Before apparatus 3, phosphorous and sulfuric acids are added to nitric acid in such amount that

the finished product contains 0.3-0.5% P₂O₅ and 0.05-0.2% ammonium sulfate. The device is equipped with two parallel ITN devices.²

In addition to nitric acid, gaseous ammonia is given to them, preheated at 2 with steam condensate to 120-130 °C. The amount of supplied nitric acid and ammonia is regulated so that at the outlet of the ITN apparatus there is a small excess of acid in the solution (2-5 g / l), which ensures complete absorption of ammonia.

A neutralization reaction takes place in the lower part of the device at a temperature of 155-170 °C; this produces a concentrated solution containing 91-92% NH₄NO₃. At the top of the device, water vapor (called juice vapor) is washed from the splash of ammonium nitrate and nitric acid vapor. Part of the heat of juice steam is used to heat nitric acid. The juice is then sent for steam cleaning and vented to the atmosphere.

Scheme of AS-72 ammonium nitrate unit:

1 - acid heater; 2 – ammonia heater; 3 – ITN devices; 4 - further neutralizer; 5 - evaporator; 6 - pressure tank; 7.8 - granulators; 9.23 - fans; 10 – washing machine; 11 - drum; 12.14 - conveyors; 13 - elevator; 15 – fluidized bed apparatus; 16 - granulation tower; 17 - assembly; 18, 20 - pumps; 19 - swimming tank; 21 - filter for swimming; 22 - air heater.

An acidic solution of ammonium nitrate is sent to the neutralizer 4; Ammonia, which is necessary for interaction with the remaining nitric acid, is included. Then the solution is sent to the evaporator 5. The resulting solution contains 99.7-99.8% nitrate, passes through the filter 21 at 175 °C and is pumped by the centrifugal submersible pump 20 into the pressure vessel 6, and then into the rectangle is sent. metal granulation tower 16.

In the upper part of the tower there are granulators 7 and 8, the lower part of which is supplied with air, which cools the drops of saltpeter falling from above. Fertilizer granules are formed when air flows around saltpeter drops from a height of 50-55 m. The temperature of the pellets at the outlet of the tower is 90-110 °C; hot pellets are cooled in a fluidized bed apparatus 15. This is a rectangular apparatus having three sections and equipped with a grid with holes. Fans provide air under the grill; this

creates a fluidized bed of nitrate granules coming from the granulation tower via a conveyor. After cooling, the air enters the granulation tower. Ammonia nitrate conveyor granules 14 serve for treatment with surfactants in a rotating drum. Then the finished fertilizer is sent to packaging through the 12th conveyor.

The air leaving the granulation tower is contaminated with ammonium nitrate particles, the juice vapor from the neutralizer and the vapor-air mixture in the evaporator contain unreacted ammonia and nitric acid, as well as carried ammonium nitrate particles.

At the top of the granulation tower, to clean these streams, six parallel scrubber type scrubbers 10 are irrigated with a 20-30% solution of ammonium nitrate, which are supplied by a pump 18 from the assembly 17. this solution is directed to the ITN neutralizer to wash the juice vapor, which is then mixed with the saltpeter solution and thus used to make the product. Purified air is sucked from the granulation tower by fan 9 and released into the atmosphere.

The technological process of obtaining ammonium nitrate consists of the following main stages: neutralization of nitric acid with gaseous ammonia, evaporation of ammonium nitrate solution, crystallization and granulation of the solution.

ITP 3 apparatus receives gaseous ammonia from heater 1 and nitric acid from heater 2 at a temperature of 80-90 0 C. In order to reduce the loss of ammonia, an excess amount of acid is reacted with steam. The ammonium nitrate solution from the device 3 is neutralized with ammonia in the next neutralizer 4 and enters the evaporator 5. rectangular granulation tower 16 for evaporation.

Technological scheme of production of ammonium nitrate.

1 - ammonia heater, 2 - nitric acid heater, 3 - ITN apparatus (using the heat of neutralization), 4 - additional neutralizer, 5 - vaporizer, 6 - pressure vessel, 7,8 - granulators, 9,23 - fans, 10 - washing machine, 11-drum, 12,14- conveyor, 13-elevator, 15-fluid bed apparatus, 16-granulation tower, 17-collector, 18,20-pump, 19-float tank, 21- float filter, 22-air heater.

In the upper part of the tower there are granulators 7 and 8, the lower part of which is supplied with air, which cools the drops of saltpeter falling from above. During the

fall of saltpeter drops from a height of 50-55 meters, when air flows around them, granules are formed, which are cooled in a fluidized bed apparatus 15. This is a right-angled apparatus with three parts and a mesh with holes. Fans supply air under the grill. From the granulation tower, a fluidized bed of saltpeter granules is formed. After cooling, the air enters the granulation tower.

The granules of the ammonium nitrate conveyor 14 are sent to the rotating drum 11 for treatment with surfactants. Then the finished fertilizer conveyor 12 is sent to the package.

The air leaving the granulation tower is contaminated with ammonium nitrate, and the juice vapor from the neutralizer contains unreacted ammonia and nitric acid, as well as entrained ammonium nitrate particles. At the top of the granulation tower, for cleaning these flows, there are six scrubbers 10 of the washing plate type operating in parallel, which are irrigated with a 20-30% saltpetre solution, which are supplied to the collecting 17. solution through a pump 18. from saltpeter and is therefore used to make products. Purified air is sucked from the granulation tower by fan 9 and released into the atmosphere.³

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is worth saying that this article has explained step by step how to make ammonium nitrate products. Technological schemes of production of ammonium nitrate were given.

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